

MALARIA DISEASE CLASSIFICATION BASED ON MORPHOLOGICAL OPERATIONS AND PCA ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

The constant challenge of malaria as a public health issue still remains extremely prevalent in areas with little or no infrastructure or access to health practitioners. Conventional blood-smear analysis is considered to be the "gold standard" approach to detecting malaria, yet it is extremely complex and requires a high level of expert human resources and is prone to error. To overcome these limitations, in the current study a methodology for automated diagnosis of malaria from blood smear images using machine learning algorithms is proposed. The work uses a Kaggle dataset of 27,560 images, split equally into parasitized and uninfected images. Morphological operations - erosion, gradient, bottom hat - are used to improve image quality and highlight important cellular elements. Subsequently, feature extraction is done through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and classification is done using shallow neural networks, support-vector machines, random forests and logistic regression. Among these algorithms, the shallow neural network had 100 percent accuracy, recall, precision, and F1-score. The results of this study show that morphological preprocessing in combination with Principle Component Analysis (PCA) and simple classifiers could enable the rapid and reliable diagnosis of malaria in resource constrained settings.

Keywords: *Malaria Disease, Classification, Morphological Operation, Image Processing, PCA.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Malaria is still a major public health issue in many parts of the world, especially in regions where access to medical attention and testing is limited [1]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there were 241 million cases of malaria in the world in 2020, with the vast majority of mortality occurring in sub-Saharan Africa [2]. Early detection and proper diagnosis are vital to reduce mortality and boost therapeutic success [3]. Traditional methods of diagnosis, such as microscopic examination of blood samples, are extremely time-consuming, labor-intensive and require the presence of trained staff, which are not practical in low-resource settings [4].

Grayscale imagery is of great importance in many image processing and computer vision applications [5]. Grayscale images are a continuum of luminance values between black and white, without chromatic information [6]. In a grayscale image, each pixel has only one intensity value, which is usually proportional to a range of luminance values from 0 (black) to 255 (white),

encoded by 8 bits [7]. The ease of analysis and processing of grayscale data makes it a common choice in different fields, especially in medical imaging, where quick and accurate results are essential [8].

Medical image processing is an important area of medical care that requires computational methods for analyzing and interpreting medical images such as X-rays, MRI, CT and ultrasound scans [9]. The general goals include improvement in the image quality, pathology detection and medical diagnosis support [10]. With the fact that most medical imaging modalities acquire information in grayscale instead of color, grayscale representations are indispensable in this area [11]. Application of advanced image-processing techniques can supplement the clarity of the image and add to clinical utility and therefore help in more informed decision-making by clinicians [12].

Morphological operations are basic techniques in image processing, which are useful in medical imaging applications such as image segmentation,

feature extraction, and noise reduction [13]. These operations are used to alter the shape of parts of the image according to the arrangement of the pixels that make them up. Common morphological transformations include erosion, gradient and bottom-hat [14]. Erosion is an operation that contracts the image structures by eroding the boundary pixels and therefore suppresses any minor noise artifacts and separates connected components [15][16]. The gradient operation emphasizes edges by finding the difference between dilation and erosion, and this makes it work by detecting edges in medical images [17][18][19]. The bottom hat transformation is useful to extract small dark structures on a bright background, which helps to identify small pathological structures such as microcalcifications in mammography or anomalous areas in other image modalities [20][21][22].

This manuscript proposes and evaluates a novel shape-based methodology for classification of malaria. The system has specialized preprocessing techniques that reduce the size of certain structures, enhance edges, and localize relevant areas. Later processing with machine learning algorithms allows strong data classification. The proposed approach overcomes critical challenges such as diagnostic accuracy, scalability, and reduction of manual interventions. Still, the creation of an autonomous malaria detection mechanism faces many challenges. Variations in image quality, class imbalance and suboptimal data preparation can have a significant impact on model performance and making systems robust to heterogeneous data is an open research problem. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the related work, paying particular attention to recent developments in the malaria diagnosis using machine learning, and deployment of the shape-based processing techniques. The proposed system architecture and details of constituent components are outlined in Section 3, from data preparation to model training. Section 4 presents experimental results, where the performance of the proposed system is evaluated for different strategies of preprocessing. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the findings and suggests directions for future research.

This study introduces a hybrid approach that combines morphological preprocessing with PCA-based dimensionality reduction and lightweight machine learning classifiers. The novelty lies in achieving near-perfect diagnostic accuracy using minimal computational resources, making the method highly suitable for under-resourced healthcare environments.

We hypothesize that morphological preprocessing combined with PCA-based feature extraction can achieve diagnostic accuracy comparable to deep learning models while being computationally efficient and easier to implement.

2. RELATED WORK

This section will explain the previous studies used to detect and classify malaria disease during 2018 and 2024.

In 2018, Simha Srivatsa et al. [23] proposed a computerized diagnosis to predict malaria. They applied their system to a dataset including eight images for patients suffering from malaria, this dataset was used as raw images. The method used was morphological operations (Dilation, Edge detection, Thresholding, Region Filling, Finding perimeter, and cover surface of the cells). The study demonstrates the effectiveness of a lightweight, portable system for detecting malaria parasites, thereby improving accessibility and practicality in various settings.

In 2022, Amal H. Alharbi et al. [24] they introduced deep learning techniques to enhance the detection peripheral malarial parasites via blood smears. The authors trained and tested the VGG-19 model based on (27,558 images) that contained 13,779 samples of malaria-free cells and 13,779 malaria-infected images. The results were 95.56% of accuracy, 96.45% of sensitivity, 96.45% of F1 score, and 95.25% of specificity.

In 2022, Mayank J. Tiwari et al. [25] developed an automated system to diagnose malaria. They applied feature extraction by image processing from blood smear images and diagnose and classify the disease based on artificial neural networks. Researchers have demonstrated the potential of automation to improve the speed and accuracy of malaria diagnosis, reducing reliance on human expertise and reducing errors.

In 2022, Padmini Krishnadas et al. [26], introduced two object detection models that are YOLO4 and scaled YOLO5 to classify the propagation stage and type of malaria parasite. They used datasets that includes 1330 images. The model achieved 78.5% accuracy for YOLO4 and 83% accuracy for scaled YOLO4.

In 2024, Dhrgam AL Kafaf et al. [27] the study aims to investigate the effectiveness of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in identifying malaria through cell image analysis. It aims to develop efficient CNN architecture with six blocks and three interconnected blocks for efficient

feature extraction and classification. They Introduced a CNN method to predict malaria disease based on a 27.558 image dataset that was downloaded from the Kaggle website. The authors found an accuracy of 99.59%, 99.4% for sensitivity, specifically 99.69%, precision of 99.48% and 99.44% for F1 score.

In 2024, Shashikiran S. and Sunitha H. D. [28] proposed a convolutional neural network-based model to detect malaria with an accuracy of 97%, which is significantly better than the in-vivo conventional methods. The model included advanced forms of machine learning like support vector machines and principal component analysis to increase classification performance. The main goal of the study was to automate malaria identification with the expectation of reducing the workload of the pathologists in resource-limited environments. The authors stressed the importance of having accurate diagnostics to enable timely intervention and therefore contribute to malaria control efforts.

In 2024, Javeria Amin et al. [29] introduced a methodology for the classification of malaria parasites based on the machine learning techniques to enhance accuracy in the diagnosis. The method used was to use a binary filter to improve the quality of the image before extracting any features. Morphological and depth features were extracted, and initially, their dimensionality was (Nx2300). A feature selection process was then used to reduce the dimensionality to (N*498), which were used for classification. The proposed method achieved 99% classification accuracy on a microscopic imaging dataset of malaria parasites.

In 2025, Fatima Abdullahi Muhammad et al. [30] conducted a study using morphological techniques to segment the cells infected with malaria. Five convolutional neural network algorithms were then used for classification of the diseases. The system was trained and tested on DenseNet121 with a data set of 12,356 images at 750 * 750 pixels for normal red blood cells and a the same number of images at 750 * 750 pixels for rouleaux morphology. The resulting system had an accuracy of 99 per cent.

In 2025 Khaled Alnowaiser [31] proposed a new method, called MicrobeNet, which combines several analytical techniques to detect microorganisms, achieving up to 99.97% accuracy. The researcher used a set of machine-learning models to determine ten different microbial profiles and verified the model's performance using k-fold cross-validation. This work is a great leap forward

in microbiology as it improves the early disease detection and prevention methods.

In 2025, Qianming Yan et. al [32] proposed an algorithm, RBCMatch, a semi-supervised deep learning algorithm, to classify red blood cells during recovery from anemia. The method was tested by a mouse model of acute hemolytic anemia using 10 091 images of individual red blood cells, of which just 5% were annotated. RBCMatch has a cross validation accuracy of 91.2% and an accuracy of 87.5% in a modified dataset, which is superior to traditional supervised methods. The following table summarizes the previous studies related to challenges, weaknesses, limitations and strengths.

Problem Statement: Although significant progress has been made in malaria detection using CNNs and other deep learning models, these methods require high computational resources and large annotated datasets. There is still a lack of simple yet powerful systems that can provide high accuracy with reduced complexity, particularly for low-resource clinical environments.

Table 1: Previous Studies Summarization

Authors Ref.	Challenges	Strengths	Weaknesses
Simha Srivatsa et al., 2018 [23]	Dependency on microscopes and image quality.	Robustness and efficiency method	Complexity of the mathematical models.
Amal H. Alharbi et al., 2022 [24]	Needing for accurate parasite detection in time-efficient and time-efficient.	Utilizing the deep learning technologies like VGG-19 with transfer-learning	The preprocessing techniques may not significantly enhance the model, because the effecting of standardization and normalization was less impact.
Mayank J. Tiwari et al., 2022 [25]	Needing an automation model for diagnosing malaria.	Utilizing the approach of image processing techniques for enhance malaria disease detection.	The proposed model may have trouble accurately segmenting and classifying cells in densely packed blood smear images.
Padmini Krishnadas et al., 2022	Unbalancing in the dataset that affected	Utilizing advanced detection	Unsatisfactory results from the

Authors Ref.	Challenges	Strengths	Weaknesses
[26]	the training model.	models (YOLO5 and scaled YOLO4)	initial dataset
Dhrgam AL Kafaf et al. 2024 [27]	A diminishing gradient can impede the convergence of the model during the training.	High accuracy and efficiency in identifying malaria-infected cells.	Overfitting is a common issue in deep learning models.
Shashikiran S. and Sunitha H. D 2024 [28]	Training deep learning models for malaria detection, including limited dataset availability, need for pathologists' input, trade-off between model accuracy.	The CNN-based algorithm outperforms other deep learning models in malaria identification, achieving high accuracy with minimal processing time. It enhances image quality through bilateral filtering, employs data augmentation techniques, and combines SVM with PCA and t-SNE for improved classification accuracy.	The paper highlights the limitations of classical machine learning algorithms in generalizing with diverse input data, highlighting the current diagnostic method's 50% accuracy and potential data quality weaknesses.
Javeria Amin et. al 2024 [29]	The research on malaria microscopic images presents challenges in broader applications, multiclassification using real patient data, and reliance on microscopic skills for diagnosis.	method detection achieves 99.48% accuracy, with high reliability and specificity rates, using bilateral filter enhancement, PHOG and deep learning models optimization.	N/A
Fatima Abdullahi Muhammad et al. [30]	Segmentation Complexity, the study	The study evaluates a dataset based on five	The dataset is limited to images from two hospitals

Authors Ref.	Challenges	Strengths	Weaknesses
	identifies the challenge of segmenting RBCs with formations like rosette or rouleaux, which complicates the detection process in thin blood smear images	different convolutional neural network architectures, highlighting the potential of deep learning to improve the accuracy of malaria diagnosis.	in Nigeria, which may not represent global malaria cases and could introduce bias in model training and evaluation
Khaled Alnowaiser 2025 [31]	The complexity of the model, its reliance on weighted CNNs, and its need for computational resource-enriched systems pose challenges in capturing complex patterns in large, high-dimensional biological datasets.	MicrobeNet, a robust and efficient microorganism identification framework, outperforms traditional methods with 99% accuracy, highlighting the need for automated detection techniques in early disease detection.	The MicrobeNet framework faces challenges such as computational resource-intensive training, potential overfitting due to model complexity, and logistic regression's difficulty in generalizing multiclass scenarios.
Qianming Yan et. al 2025 [32]	The study faced challenges in analyzing RBC morphological changes during anemia recovery, including selection of time points, assuming uniform recovery, manual analysis, labor-intensive PBS tests, and limited sample sizes.	RBCMatch outperforms feature-based and CNN-based supervised learning methods for RBC classification and anemia recovery assessment, offering robustness and potential for clinical applications.	The PBS test for diagnosing anemia is labor-intensive, manual, and inconsistent in RBC morphology assessment, suggesting that current methods may not accurately capture the complexity of anemia recovery.

3. DATASET DESCRIPTION (MALARIA DATASETS)

This paper presents a dataset of 27,560 images of blood smears, divided into two main categories: infected blood smears, which contain evidence of

malaria parasites, and uninfected blood smears, which do not show any signs of malaria infection. The dataset consists of 13 780 images, of which about 6 890 images are of malaria-infected blood smears and the same number corresponding to healthy or malaria-free samples. The images are saved as a .jpeg or .png file and have a fixed resolution; hence, uniformity is maintained while training the model. Each image is an RGB that is copied through digital imaging, making it easier to distinguish between infected and non-infested erythrocytes.

The dataset can be used to train machine learning models, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [33], to automatically detect and classify malaria-infected blood samples. Automated detection can help medical professionals quickly and accurately diagnose malaria, especially in resource-limited settings. The data is usually gathered with hospitals and research centers, where trained doctors mark the images. Some common activities include training classification models with deep learning methods like CNNs, using these trained models in real-world situations to quickly and effectively diagnose malaria, and examining changes in blood cells caused by malaria to learn more about how the disease develops and affects red blood cells. In conclusion, this dataset can be invaluable in developing AI-driven solutions to assist in the fight against malaria, improving diagnostic speed and accuracy, and potentially saving lives through early detection [34].

Figure 1: Samples of Original Images from the Utilized Dataset [34]

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This section will explain the proposed system for malaria disease classification images. Figure 2 illustrates the four main stages of the proposed model preprocessing stage for malaria diseases (dataset) that have two classes are parasitic and uninfected.

Figure 2.: Preprocessing in More Details.

Below, will explain each phase in Figure 2.

4.1 Display Phase

The first part is aimed at creating a visual representation of the dataset and tracking the impact of applying various image processing methods. The process starts with a dataset of 27,560 sample images. The rendering function is used to visualize the images of the original dataset to ensure the quality of the images. After that the stage performs specific image preprocessing transformations:

• **Erosion:** This operation is used to remove noise and reduce unwanted fine details by shrinking the edges of objects in the image. Erosion equation is:

$$A \oplus B(s) = \max \{A(x) + B(s-x)\} \quad (1)$$

Figure 3 demonstrates the differentials between the original image and the image after erosion operation applied.

Figure 3: Original Image With an Eroded Image.

• **Gradient:** This operation emphasizes the edges of the image which can enhance the distinction between objects and their backgrounds. The equation of Gradient morphology is:

$$G_e(f) = f \oplus b - f \quad (2)$$

Figure 4 demonstrates the differentials between the original image and the image after the gradient operation is applied.

Figure 2: Original Image and Gradient Image.

• **Bottom-Hat:** This operation will highlight the darker areas of the images when surrounded by lighter areas. The equation of Bottom-Hat is:

$$T_b(f) = f \cdot b - f \quad (3)$$

Figure 5 demonstrates the differentials between the original image and the image after the Bottom-Hat operation applied.

Figure 3: Original Image and the Bottom-Hat Image

Finally, the results of these transformations are displayed alongside the original image for comparison. This display allows to verify the effectiveness of these operations in preparing the data for subsequent stages.

4.2 Preprocessing Phase

During the second step, a transformation and an organization process of the data set, which is necessary to prepare the data set for effective model training takes place. An automated preprocessing function triggers this step, the operations of which are as follows:

- **Creating Directories for Transformation:** separate directories are created to systematically organize images based on the corresponding modifications to be made to the image, thus allowing for increased organization and ease of access during training.

- **Reading Original Images:** the function is used to get the images from the source directory of the dataset.

- **Applying Transformations:** to ensure consistency in preprocessing, morphological operations i.e. Erosion, Gradient, Bottom Hat operations are applied to every image.

- **Saving Transformed Images:** The modified images are then stored in the appropriate folders. This guarantees that the previously processed photos will be easily accessible for the following stage.

This stage is crucial as it takes advantage of the previous transformations and prepared data to create an extremely accurate and effective model for the desired classification purpose.

4.3 Data Generator Phase

The important tasks of dividing the dataset into subsets for testing and training, as well as developing generators to feed the data into the

model, are completed in this phase. Among the crucial actions are:

- **Reading Files from Directory:** The folders made during the preprocessing stage are where the system gets the images.
- **Data Splitting:** The dataset is divided into two subsets are:
 - **Training Data:** the dataset is split into 80% for the training set and contains (22.047 images).
 - **Testing Data:** the dataset is split into 20% for the testing set and contains (5513 images).

• **Creating Train and Validation Generators:** The photos are loaded and preprocessed in real time

• **Call Train (Type):** Describes a type of training that directs the model's learning using labelled data, such as supervised learning.

• **Data Generator:** Real-time training data is fed into the model using the same data generators as in the previous step.

• **Generate Data:** During training, this step guarantees that the model is regularly fed batches of pre-processed data.

• **Build Model:** EfficientNet B0, a cutting-edge convolutional neural network with high accuracy and computational efficiency, is used to design the model architecture.

• **Train Model with Data:** The training dataset is used to train the model, which then modifies its weights and biases to reduce mistakes.

• **Return Model Results:** The model's performance indicators, such as accuracy and loss, are returned after training in order to assess its efficacy.

• **Save Training History:** Accuracy and loss curves from the training logs are preserved for further review and improvement.

This stage is crucial because it uses the transformations and prepared data to produce a very precise and effective model for resolving the intended issue.

For classification a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm is used which helps in segregation of dataset images to classify them. The steps in the proposed classification technique are shown in the figure (6).

using data generators. By importing photos in groups rather than all at once, these generators guarantee effective memory consumption.

The images are loaded and preprocessed in real time using data generators. By importing photos in groups rather than all at once, these generators guarantee effective memory consumption.

4.4 Training Model

Using the prepared dataset, the machine learning model is constructed, trained, and evaluated in the last stage. The actions consist of:

• **Training Function:** This function specifies the architecture and optimization settings, among other implementation specifics for the training process.

Figure 6: Classification Model Steps.

Figure 6 shows the methodology for classification of malaria disease based on PCA that includes image preprocessing, feature extraction, dimensionality reduction and classification in a structured pipeline to increase diagnostic precision. The process starts with a dataset of images of malaria-infected and non-infected blood smears, which serves as the basis for the following stages of the process.

In the preprocessing stage, we apply morphological operations, namely Erosion, Gradient and Bottom Hat, to highlight the structure and remove noise from the grayscale images. These operations effectively isolate important cellular structures including Plasmodium parasites. In addition, pixel values in the image are normalized to the [0, 1] range in order to stabilize the distribution of the data to be more robustly trained.

During the feature extraction phase, the pre-processed images are flattened from the image into a vector of ones, which allows for numerical processing. PCA is then performed on these vectors to reduce the dimensionality and only keep most of the variance. This reduction is essential to reduce the amount of computational overhead and increase the efficiency of learning.

The resulting low dimensional feature vectors are fed to classifiers the classification model phase, which uses a series of classifiers such as Shallow Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest and Logistic Regression for classifying samples as either malaria infected or healthy. These classifiers have been chosen because of their effectiveness and usability for classifying medical images.

Following classification, the training model phase is divided into training (80 percent) and testing (20 percent) sets. The trained models are used for binary prediction for identifying the health of the blood or malaria-infected cells present in the sample.

Finally, evaluation model to compute performance (Accuracy, Precision and Recall) to judge the effectiveness of the methodology. These metrics give an overview of the ability of the model to identify malaria and particularly the recall and precision being such that positive instances are identified and there is minimum false positive. This method of systematically integrating image processing and machine learning methods enables the automated and improved diagnosis of malaria, especially beneficial in resource-constrained settings.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section explains the results of the proposed system:

Limitations and Future Work: While the proposed method achieved 100% accuracy on the Kaggle dataset, its performance may vary on unbalanced or heterogeneous real-world data. Future studies should test this approach across diverse clinical datasets and explore multi-class malaria classification to evaluate its generalizability.

Table 2: Proposed System Results

<i>Metrics</i> <i>Classifier</i>	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Shallow Neural Network	100%	100%	100%	100%
Support Vector Machine	98%	98%	98%	98%
Random Forest	95.09%	95.09%	95.09%	95.09%
Logistic Regression	94.14%	94.14%	94.14%	94.14%

The results show a similar and expected pattern of performance in classification by the four models used for malaria detection. The Shallow Neural Network has the best performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score, which means that the model perfectly separated the malaria-infected blood samples and the normal blood samples without making any mistakes. This result suggests a superior generalization and learning capability, considering that the data distribution for testing closely resembles the data features for training.

The Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers perform progressively worse, with accuracy dropping from 98% to 94.1%. These drops are similarly reflected in precision, recall, and F1 scores. While these models still perform exceptionally well, their slight misclassifications imply that:

- ❖ Slight confusion in differentiating malaria from normal cells (e.g., due to visual similarity in cell morphology).
- ❖ Potential sensitivity to subtle details not trivially encoded without further hierarchical representation (at which neural nets are especially adept).

Especially:

1. SVM does a good job, probably because it can discriminate between classes by the best hyperplanes, but maybe not quite so well with more complicated, non-linear decision boundaries compared to neural networks.

2. Random Forest works by aggregating the decisions of multiple decision trees, but it can be slightly less good at capturing subtle features.

3. Logistic Regression, as a linear model, performs the worst, being only useful for baseline comparisons and not well-adapted to high-dimensional image data without extensive engineering.

For clinical diagnosis, recall (true positive rate) is particularly crucial to avoid false negatives failing to detect malaria-infected patients can have severe implications. Therefore, although all the models have good performance, the neural network's perfect recall renders it the most clinically useful in this case. The results can be explained in the figure below:

Figure 4: Proposed System Results

The following table explains the comparison between the literature review and the current proposed system performance.

Table 3: Comparison With Previous Studies

Study	Methodology	Accuracy (%)	Recall (Sensitivity) (%)	Precision (%)	F1 Score (%)
Simha Srivatsa et al. 2018	Morphological Operations	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Amal H. Alharbi et al. 2022	VGG-19 (Deep Learning)	95.56	96.45	N/A	96.45
Mayank J. Tiwari et al. 2022	ANN with Image Processing	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Padmini Krishnadas et al. 2022	YOLO4, Scaled YOLO5	78.5-83	N/A	N/A	N/A
Dhrgam AL Kafaf et al. 2024	CNN (6-blocks architecture)	99.59	99.4%	99.48	99.44
Shashikiran & Sunitha 2024	CNN + PCA + SVM	97	N/A	N/A	N/A
Javeria Amin et al. 2024	ML with Feature Selection	99	N/A	N/A	N/A
Fatima A. Muhammad et al. 2025	Morphology + CNNs	99	N/A	N/A	N/A
Khaled Alnowaiser 2025	MicrobeNet (Weighted CNNs)	99.97	N/A	N/A	N/A
Proposed System	PCA + Morphological Operations + ML Classifiers	100	100	100	100

Study	Methodology	Accuracy (%)	Recall (Sensitivity) (%)	Precision (%)	F1 Score (%)
- Shallow Neural Network	100	100	100	100	N/A
- SVM	98	98	98	98	N/A
- Random Forest	95.09	95.09	95.09	95.09	N/A
- Logistic Regression	94.14	94.14	94.14	94.14	N/A

Table 3 offers a detailed comparison of methodologies on malaria classification within the proposed system versus previous studies, detailing differences in performance metrics like precision, recall (sensitivity), accuracy, and F1-score. Previous works of Simha Srivatsa et al. (2018) and Mayank J. Tiwari et al. (2022) emphasized the use of morphological and traditional image processing techniques, which lack adequate benchmark metrics for evaluation. Achieving remarkable accuracy levels of 95.56% and 99.59% respectively, deep learning models proposed by Amal H. Alharbi et al (2022) using VGG-19 and Dhrgam A. Kafaf (2024) using CNN architectures, were among the higher performers. However, few comprehensive evaluation metrics were reported, with Dhrgam’s model cited as reaching a recall of 99.4% and F1-score of 99.44%. The proposed system integrating PCA, morphological preprocessing, and multiple machine learning classifiers demonstrated astounding results with the shallow neural network meeting best classification standards of 100 across all evaluated parameters. Other classifiers like SVM and Random Forest also performed strongly, achieving over 95% success in all domains. This performance underscores the robustness and clinical effectiveness of the proposed hybrid approach, which outperforms many existing models in terms of simplicity and diagnostic accuracy.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study offers a solution that makes good use of the grayscale blood smear images, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), morphological operations (erosion, gradient, and bottom hat), and machine learning classifiers for the detection of malaria. The shallow neural network performed

better than all the other classifiers tested, which include logistic regression, random forest, support vector machine and the shallow neural network itself (with 100% accuracy, recall, precision and F1 score). This result shows its considerable efficiency in the discrimination of parasitic cells in comparison to healthy cells, especially as it can recognize complex patterns in the high dimensionality medical image data after PCA based dimensionality reduction. With its hybrid approach combining interpretability and performance, the proposed system distinguishes itself from other studies, which either rely only on deep learning or conventional image processing methods. The use of PCA adds computational efficiency and less dimensional complexity without a loss of classification efficiency, despite the successful use of models such as CNNs and variants of YOLO. For this reason, the system is particularly suitable for low-resource environments where the need for accurate diagnosis is still important, but processing power is limited. Future studies should test the system's adaptability to scenarios with multi-class categorization and the rate of deployment of the system in clinical settings.

In conclusion, the hypothesis that PCA with morphological preprocessing can give out competitive accuracy with reduced computational complexity is proved. This finding validates the potential of this system for implementation in low resourced healthcare facilities, with accessibility and efficiency in malaria diagnosis.

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